

Remote control system for unipolar stepper motor

Petru Livinti

¹Department of Energetics and Computer Science, University "Vasile Alecsandri" of Bacau, Romania

Abstract: In this work, a remote control system for the unipolar stepper motor was presented. The remote control of the unipolar stepper motor was realized by radio waves on the frequency of 2.4 GHz. For the remote transmission of commands, two circuits were used: a transmitter circuit and a receiver circuit. The two circuits include a developing board each, of type Arduino Uno and a shield NRF24L01. For generating the reference signal a potentiometer in the transmitter circuit has been used and for supplying the stepping motor a driver of type ULN 2003A has been used in the receiver circuit. The author's contributions are: - elaboration of two programs in the Arduino IDE programming environment for the two circuits – transmitter and receiver- elaboration of the electrical diagrams of the two circuits with the help of the Fritzing program. The experimental results have proved the exact functioning of the remote control system of the unipolar stepper motor.

Keywords: unipolar stepper motor, Arduino Uno, shield NRF24L01

*Corresponding Author

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I. Introduction

Due to their rotation accuracy, stepping motors are a viable solution for the driving systems controlled in open cycle. Since the rotation error is low in case of the stepping motors and does not cumulate at a succession of steps, their usage is also recommended for their low energy consumption. The disadvantages of using stepping motors are: - a very complex control process, especially in case of bipolar stepper motors, - necessity of drivers for controlling the electric current passing through the phase coils of the motor. The stepper motors are also used for driving the elevators, [1] and positioning systems, [3], [4], [5], [6]. The Bluetooth remote control system is used on elevators, [2]. The wireless control system is used for stepping motors, as shown in the work [7]. This work aims at integrating a remote control system of a unipolar stepping motor built with two developing boards Arduino Uno and two shields NRF24L01. This control system is wireless. The remote control through radio waves at the frequency of 2.4 GHz allows the usage of the unipolar stepping motor in the structure of those driving systems that can be used in toxic environments or in spaces inaccessible to human operators.

II Materials and Methods

2.1 Objectives of the Research

The objectives of the research in the field of remote control systems of the unipolar stepping motors are:

- Improving the energetic efficiency of the unipolar stepping motors
- Elaborating programs for the transmitter and receiver circuits for the developing boards Arduino Uno
- Lowering the costs of the remote control systems of the unipolar stepping motors used into the structure of industrial driving systems
- Enhancing the reliability of the remote control systems of the unipolar stepping motors

For implementing and validating the remote control system of a unipolar stepping motor an experimental stand has been built in the Laboratory of Electrical Machinery and Drives of the University "Vasile Alecsandri" of Bacau.

2.2 Description of the Experimental Stand

Based on two developing boards Arduino Uno and two Shields NRF24L01 the remote control system of a unipolar stepping motor has been built. The structure of this remote control system of a unipolar stepping motor is presented at Fig. 1 below.

Fig. 1 Structure of the experimental stand for remote control system of a stepping motor

The transmitter circuit is composed of the developing board Arduino Uno 1 connected to the Laptop 1. The reference rate will be settled through a potentiometer connected to the board Arduino Uno 1. For transmitting the control signal the shield NRF24L01 will be used. The Laptop 1 is used for programming the developing board Arduino Uno 1 as well as for supplying the elements in the structure of the transmitter circuit. The receiver circuit is composed of the developing board Arduino Uno 2 connected to the Laptop 2. To the developing board Arduino Uno 2 the driver for stepper motors ULN 2003A is connected, as well as the display circuit LCD 1602 and the shield NRF24L01. The stepper motor will be connected to the driver ULN 2003A and will be supplied at a voltage of 9 V. The Laptop 2 is used for programming the developing board Arduino Uno 2 and for supplying the elements in the structure of the receiver circuit.

2.2.1. Characteristics of the shield NRF24L01:

- „Supply voltage: 1.9 - 3.6 V. d. C.;
- Current consumption: 11.3 mA at an emission power of 0 dBm;
- Current consumption: 13.5mA at data reception at 2 Mbps;

- Current consumption: 26 uA in standby mode;
- Current consumption: 900 nA in power down mode;
- Speed of 250 kbps, 1Mbps or 2Mbps;
- SPI communication interface”;

The signals through radio waves are transmitted at a frequency of 2.4 GHz.

The meaning of the pins for the shield NRF24L01 is shown at Fig. 2.

Fig.2. Meaning of the pins

VCC – supply from 1,9 up to 3,3 V

GND – ground

MOSI – SPI input of serial data

MISO - SPI output of serial data

SCK - SPI clock

CSN – the low status on this pin indicates that the controller wants to communicate with this module.

CE – reception and transmission of the signal. In the receiving mode the high status indicates that the reception is required. In the transmission mode the pulse sends a pack of data.

IRQ – interruption output. It generates a pulse of low status when the data wait to receive or when the data have been sent correctly.

2.2.2. Developing Board Arduino Uno

The developing board Arduino Uno is a platform that uses the micro controller Atmega 328P, Fig. 3. This platform is easily usable and can takeover information from a various range of sensors, by means of the input pins. After processing the information coming from sensors, Arduino Uno can transmit commands through the output pins to a various range of elements, such as motors, led’s, actuators etc. The developing board Arduino Uno has 6 pins for analogue inputs, 14 pins for digital inputs/outputs (out of which 6 can be used as PWM outputs), a quartz oscillator of 20 MHz, a supply socket, a USB connexion and a reset button.

Fig.3. Developing board Arduino Uno

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Electric Diagram of the Transmitter Circuit

The electric diagram of the transmitter circuit is shown at Fig. 4.

Fig.4. Electric diagram of the transmitter circuit

The program for the developing board Arduino Uno in the structure of the transmitter circuit is:

```

Emitator_mpp | Arduino 1.8.13
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
Emitator_mpp $
1 #include <SPI.h>
2 #include <nRF24L01.h>
3 #include <RF24.h>
4 RF24 radio(7, 8); // CE, CSN
5 const byte address[6] = "00001";
    
```

```

6  int LED =9;
7  int analogwrite;
8  |
9  void setup() {
10     Serial.begin(9600);
11     radio.begin();
12     delay(100);
13     radio.openWritingPipe(address);
14     radio.setPALevel(RF24_PA_MIN);
15     radio.stopListening();
16 }
17 void loop() {
18     int pot=analogRead(A1);
19     if(radio.write(&pot, sizeof(pot)))
20         analogwrite=(255./1023.)*pot ;
21         analogWrite(LED, analogwrite);
22         Serial.println(analogwrite);
23         delay(100);
24 }

```

3.2. Electric Diagram of the Receiver Circuit

The electric diagram of the receiver circuit is shown at Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Electric diagram of the receiver circuit

The program for the developing board Arduino Uno in the structure of the receiver circuit is:

Receptor_mpp | Arduino 1.8.13

File Edit Sketch Tools Help

```
Receptor_mpp $
1  #include <Wire.h>
2  #include <LiquidCrystal_I2C.h>
3  #include <Stepper.h>
4  #include <SPI.h>
5  #include <nRF24L01.h>
6  #include <RF24.h>
7  RF24 radio(7, 8); // CE, CSN
8  const byte address[6] = "00001";
9  #define STEPS 100
10 Stepper stepper(STEPS, 3, 4, 5, 6);
11 int previous = 0;
12 LiquidCrystal_I2C lcd(0x3F,16,2);
13 int valoarel;
14
15 void setup()
16 {
17     Serial.begin(9600);
18     lcd.init();
19     lcd.init();
20     radio.begin();
21     lcd.backlight();
22     delay(100);
23     radio.openReadingPipe(0, address);
24     radio.setPALevel(RF24_PA_MIN);
25     radio.startListening();
26     stepper.setSpeed(30);
27 }
28
29 void loop()
30 {
31     radio.available(); {
32     int valoare=0;
33     radio.read(&valoare, sizeof(valoare));
34     valoarel = map(valoare, 0, 1023, 0, 255);
35     stepper.step(valoare - previous);
36     previous = valoare;
37     lcd.setCursor(0,0);
38     lcd.print(valoarel);
39     Serial.println(valoarel);
40 }
41 }
```

3.3. Functioning of the Experimental Stand

By means of the potentiometer the remote command is given for settling the rpm of the stepper motor. The voltage analogue signal is transformed into PWM signal (pulse width modulation) and sent through the developing board Arduino Uno 1 and the transmitter circuit NRF24L01 by radio waves to the receiver circuit. The receiver circuit may be located at a distance of maximum 20 metres. The receiver circuit captures the signal sent by the transmitter circuit through the developing board Arduino Uno 2 and the receiver circuit NRF24L01. The control signal is sent from the developing board Arduino Uno 2 to the supply driver of the unipolar stepper motor ULN 2003A. The stepper motor will be controlled by the driver ULN 2003A in function of the control signal sent by the transmitter circuit through radio waves to the receiver circuit. For supplying the unipolar stepper motor a D.C. voltage source of 9 Volts has been used. The value of the filling factor of the control signal for the driver ULN 2003A is displayed on the display LCD 1602.

3.4. Discussions

Experimental determinations have been performed in the laboratory of Electrical Machinery and Drives of the University "Vasile Alecsandri" of Bacau. In function of the value of the reference signal the rpm of the stepper motor has been modified. During the experimental determinations no losses of steps of the unipolar stepper motor have been found. In order to increase the distance between the transmitter and receiver NRF24L01 circuits with aerials may be used. The remote control can be used in the case of the electric driving systems with unipolar stepper motors used in spaces inaccessible to human operators.

4. Conclusions

This work presented an experimental stand for the remote control of the unipolar stepper motor. This stand is composed of a transmitter circuit and a receiver circuit. The two circuits include a developing board Arduino Uno and a shield NRF24L01 each. For generating the reference signal a potentiometer in the transmitter circuit has been used and for supplying the stepper motor the driver ULN 2003A in the receiver circuit has been used. In the structure of the receiver circuit the display LCD 1602 has also been used, for displaying the control signal of the unipolar stepper motor. For implementing and validating the remote control system of the unipolar stepper motor two programs have been elaborated in the programming environment Arduino IDE for the two circuits – transmitter and receiver. The communication between the two circuits has been performed through radio waves at a frequency of 2.4 GHz. The remote control of the unipolar stepper motor has functioned similarly to direct control system of the same. In perspective, this remote control of the unipolar stepper motor could also be implemented for: elevators, positioning systems, industrial robots.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest

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Professor dr. ing. Petru Livinti

